

ADSORPTION OF CERTAIN ANIONS AND CERTAIN CATIONS IN WATER RESOURCES USING A MODIFIED LOCAL KAOLIN SORBENT

O.O. Boboyev¹, D.K. Khandamova², Sh.P. Nurullayev³, R.J. Eshmetov⁴

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, doctoral student¹

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, PhD assistant²

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Professor³

Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, associate professor⁴

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Abstract. This research paper investigated the colloid-chemical properties of adsorption of some anions (chlorine, sulfur) in water resources of sorbent materials obtained by modifying AKS-30 and AKS-70 brands of kaolin, which are considered local raw materials of our republic. The colloidal-chemical properties of these sorbents were studied in terms of their adsorption of certain heavy metal ions (Si, So, Sr, Fe, Zn, Ni, Sr) from water resources.

Keywords: local raw materials, kaolin, modification, sorbent, sorption, anions, heavy metal ions, colloid-chemical properties.

In recent years, attention to surface phenomena related to colloidal chemistry has rapidly developed, but insufficient discussion and analysis of the obtained results have been reflected. The adsorption process has proven to be an effective and efficient method in oil and gas processing, organic synthesis, animal and vegetable oil purification, medical production, water resource purification, and other industrial sectors. At the same time, the adsorption method is widely used in chemical analysis and scientific research [1-3]. Unlike physical and physicochemical methods (distillation, crystallization, dialysis, etc.), the process of adsorption is distinguished by the dependence of the chemical nature of the substances that make up the system's phases. In this case, the value of the adsorption potential (ε) plays an important role in adsorbing disperse systems[4-5]. The adsorption potential has a maximum value at the boundary between the adsorbent and the adsorption volume, and is zero at the boundary between the adsorption volume and the gas phase[6-7]. Based on this, new composite adsorbents with specific compositions are developed using local raw materials and industrial waste. Their morphology, molecular structure, physicochemical properties, and sorption mechanisms are studied using modern analytical methods.

The value of the adsorption potential decreases as the substance absorbed by the adsorbent surface moves away ($\varepsilon_1 > \varepsilon_2 > \varepsilon_3$). The maximum adsorption potential is observed near the surface of the adsorbent and is determined by the formula:

$$\varepsilon = dG = \int_p^{p_s} V \cdot dp = \int_p^{p_s} \frac{RT}{P} dp = RT \int_p^{p_s} \frac{dp}{P} = RT \ln \frac{p_s}{P};$$
$$\varepsilon = RT \ln \frac{p_s}{P},$$

Scientific literature demonstrates changes in adsorption potential in relation to the amount of adsorbed substance. Therefore, the change in adsorption potential of the adsorbent was

investigated corresponding to the amount of chloride ion adsorption in modified Angren kaolin (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Characteristic diagram of the adsorption potential based on the amount of chloride ion adsorption in modified Angren kaolin

According to the change in the adsorption potential of chloride ions on the modified Angren kaolin, the adsorption potential at the initial part of adsorption at $V_{адс}=0.0078 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$ is equal to $\epsilon=7856.8 \text{ J/mol}$, and with the saturation of the adsorbent surface, at $V_{адс}=0.0298 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$, the adsorption potential sharply decreases to $\epsilon=865.9 \text{ J/mol}$. Subsequently, it was determined that as the adsorbent approaches saturation levels, the adsorption potential tends to zero according to the relationship $f= (V_{адс})$. To determine the surface area of a solid (adsorbents and catalysts), the selected adsorbate must be chemically inert. The saturated vapor pressure of the adsorbate should be sufficiently high at the experimental adsorption temperature, meaning that the relative pressure range ($P/P_s=0.01-0.6$) should allow for the measurement of adsorption with the required accuracy. Typically, the amount of adsorption is measured starting from a temperature of 293°C at the boiling point of substances in the liquid phase. Figure 2 below shows the correspondence of the adsorption isotherms of chlorine and sulfur ions with composite sorbent materials obtained by modifying Angren kaolin to the equation of the BET theory [8].

As can be seen from the data, the application of the BET theory equations in the adsorption of chlorine and sulfur ions on modified kaolin adsorbents across all relative pressure ranges is observed in a straight line. It can be seen that the adsorption of chloride ions on adsorbents consists of two straight-line substates. In one of them, this was observed at a relative pressure in the range of 0.10-0.25. This diversity can be due to several reasons [10]. The area of filling the monolayer capacity of the adsorbent is determined by the constant value C . In such cases, a straight line is observed in the pressure range of $0.05 < P/P_s < 0.20-0.35$ in the range of 60-150 points. If the constant C has a smaller value, then the capacitance of the monolayer occurs in the lower relative pressure range.

The second reason may be the presence of micropores in the adsorbent, where adsorption is high at low relative pressures, which makes a significant contribution to the amount of adsorption. It should also be noted that calculations using BET theory allow for reliable results if the adsorption isotherm belongs to type II or IV.

Sorption isotherms were obtained for the adsorption process of chlorine and sulfur ions by new sorbent materials created based on modified Angren kaolin according to Langmuir's equation.

The adsorption isotherms according to the Langmuir equation $\frac{C_p}{G} = \frac{1}{\beta} * G_{\infty}$ are shown in Figure 3 (a,b). It has been established that the adsorption process of Cl and C ions on modified kaolin adsorbents occurs according to the Langmuir equation according to experiments.

Figure 2. The expression of the adsorption isotherms of chlorine and sulfur ions on modified Angren kaolin in the coordinates of the linear form of the BET equation.

Figure 3. Isotherms of adsorption of Cl-and C-2 ions on modified Angren kaolin sorbents: 1-700C; 2 - 500°C; 3-300C; 4-200C.

The sorption isotherms for chlorine and sulfur ions of new sorbent materials based on modified AKS-30 and AKS-70 kaolins were obtained using the Dubinin-Radushkevich equation (Fig. 4).

The adsorption isotherms obtained from the experiments showed that the amount of adsorbed substance during the separation of various ions from solutions using porous sorbents occurs with the same value found based on the Dubinin-Radushkevich and Langmuir equations[11-12].

Nowadays, adsorbents are widely used globally for removing organic substances from wastewater. Therefore, studying the physicochemical and sorption properties of sorbents with

magnetic properties is of great importance [13-14]. The process of adsorbing organic substances from aqueous solutions depends on the nature of the surface and the porosity of the adsorbent [15]. Based on this, new composite adsorbents with specific compositions are developed using local raw materials and industrial waste. Their morphology, molecular structure, physicochemical properties, and sorption mechanisms are studied using modern analytical methods.

Figure 4. Isotherms of adsorption of chlorine and sulfur ions in sorbents based on modified Angren kaolin.

Results and discussion. The composite adsorbents created based on the modified kaolin grades AKS-30 and AKS-70 were tested for purifying wastewater containing heavy metal ions. The obtained results are presented in Table 1. According to the table, the sorbents demonstrated the ability to effectively remove heavy metal ions from wastewater within the range of 93-98.0%, meeting the permissible limits set by state standards.

Table 1.

The efficiency of cleaning some heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions (E, %)

Metal ions	Initial concentration (C _H), mg/dm ³	Concentration at equilibrium (C _p), mg/dm ³	E, %	REK (ПДК), mg/dm ³
Fe(II) ва Fe(III)	1,19	0,02	98,3	0,3
Cu (II)	4,40	0,16	96,4	1,0
Zn (II)	0,65	0,05	92,3	5,0
Ni (II)	0,85	0,08	93,0	0,1-0,2

The interaction of heavy metal ions in wastewater with modified kaolin-based adsorbents was studied using a static method. In this process, the solution-to-sorbent mass ratio was 1:100, 1:150, and 1:200; the particle size was 0.4 mm; the process temperature was 293°C; and the stirring speed of the reaction mixture was 400 rpm. Under practical application conditions, the porosity of adsorbents plays a significant role. Adsorbents generally exhibit four types of porosity: non-porous, uniformly large porous, uniformly small porous, and non-uniform porous adsorbents. The degree of surface filling (θ) of the adsorbents is expressed using the following equation:

$$\theta = \exp[-(F/E)^n]$$

Here, F is the decrease in free energy, expressed as $F = RT \ln^* P_s/P$ ga, E - is the adsorption energy; Θ - is the degree of filling of the adsorption phase, defined as $\Theta = a/a_\infty$; n - is an integer (1, 2, 3, ...); P - is the equilibrium pressure; P_s - is the saturated vapor pressure; a - is the specific adsorption. It is recommended to determine the adsorption energy using a graph constructed using the equation $lga = lga_\infty - 0.434 (F/E)^n$. The above-mentioned Dubinin-Radushkevich equation for the adsorption process involving solutions can be expressed as follows:

$$lga = lga_\infty - 2,303 \frac{R^2 T^2}{E^2} \left(\lg \frac{C_s}{C} \right)^2, \text{ or}$$

$$lg \alpha V^* = lg V_a - \frac{2,303 - R^2 T^2}{E^2} \lg \left(\frac{C_s}{C} \right)^2.$$

where a is the specific adsorption at a specific temperature (T) and concentration (C , mol/g); C_s - concentration of saturated solution, mol/m³; V^* - molar volume of the adsorbent, m³/mol; V_a - relative adsorption volume, m³/g; E - is the adsorption energy, R - is the universal gas constant. Depending on the selectivity of the adsorbent, the composition of the solution, the chemical potential of the substances, the surface tension, and the surface area of interphase separation change during the sorption process. The chemical potential (M_i) of a solution containing component i is given by the following equation:

$$\mu_i = \mu_i^0 + RT \ln \alpha_i^*$$

Here, α_i is the activity of the solution, and it is equal to the value of C_i divided by the coefficient of activity f . This equation can also be expressed with respect to the adsorption volume, V_a then

$$\mu_{iads} = \mu_{iads}^0 + RT \ln \alpha_{iads}^*$$

When interphase equilibrium is established during adsorption, the value of their chemical potential is also equal, i.e., $M_i = M_{i,ads}$.

Then, compared to the above equations

$$\mu_i + RT \ln C_i f_i = \mu_{i,ads}^0 + RT \ln C_{i,ads} f_{iads}$$

$$- (\mu_{i,ads}^0 - \mu_i) = RT \ln \frac{C_{i,ads} f_{iads}}{C_i f_i} = -\Delta G_i = \text{const}$$

Figure 5. The adsorption isotherm of heavy metal ions (Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+}) by modified kaolin adsorbents (using Langmuir's model). 1- Cu^{2+} , 2- Zn^{2+} , 3- Zn^{2+} , 4- Ni^{2+} .

Therefore, in the process of adsorption from solutions, the decrease in the amount of standard free energy is always constant, and the value of dG does not depend on the concentration

of the component molecules in the phases and the interaction of the component molecules in the solution. Therefore, dF can be expressed as follows.

$$-\Delta G_i = \mu_{i,ads}^0 - \mu_i^0 = RT \ln \frac{C_{i,ads} f_{i,ads}}{C_i f_i} = RT \ln K_i$$

from which,

$$\frac{C_{i,ads} f_{i,ads}}{C_i f_i} = K_i$$

resulting in equality. In practice, this equation is an isotherm equation for the adsorption of component i from aqueous solutions. The adsorption isotherm of heavy metal ions (Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cr^{6+} , Ni^{2+}) in aqueous solutions by modified kaolin sorbent materials is shown in Figure 5.

The equilibrium state of the metal ion adsorption process in aqueous solutions is proportional to the surface area of the liquid phase adsorbents and is expressed by the following equation:

$$\frac{da}{d\theta \cdot d\tau} = \beta_{ads}(a_{muv} - a_\tau) \text{ yoki } \frac{dC}{d\theta \cdot d\tau} = \beta_c(C_\tau - C_{muv})$$

The driving force of the process is a certain unit of time t and the difference of concentrates ($C_\tau - C_{muv}$), when equilibrium is established. β and β_c in the equations are called mass transfer velocities. Based on the inverse value of β , i.e. mass transfer $1/\beta_{ads}$ or $1/\beta_c = R_c$, the above equations can be written as follows:

$$\frac{da}{d\theta \cdot d\tau} = \frac{1}{R_{ads}}(a_{muv} - a_\tau) \text{ yoki } \frac{dC}{d\theta \cdot d\tau} = \frac{1}{R_c}(C_\tau - C_{muv})$$

The value of β directly depends on the interaction of the liquid with the adsorbent during the adsorption process, as well as on the size of the adsorbent particles and its porosity structure.

Conclusion. The experiments conducted on the adsorption isotherms of chlorine and sulfur ions with new sorbent materials based on modified Angren kaolin belong to type 1, the adsorbent has a microporous structure and accounts for 60% of the total porosity of the adsorbent. Thus, based on the research results, it was found that adsorption of chlorine and sulfur ions in water resources using modified adsorbents yielded positive results, and due to the presence of sorption and ion exchange properties, it is possible to widely use them in wastewater treatment.

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